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of Basel**

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VALISE

Values in School Education
Wertebildung in der Schule

Project Report

The Formation of Children's Values in School: A Study on Value Development Among Primary School Children in Swit- zerland and the United Kingdom

September 2020 - August 2022

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Project Report

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Table of Contents

List of Abbreviations	5
1.Introduction to this project report	6
2. Results of data collections	6
2.1 Descriptive description of the sample.....	6
2.1.1 Sample of pupils	7
2.1.2 Sample of teachers	8
3. Theoretical and methodical anchoring	9
4. Selection of initial analyses of the sample	14
4.1 Value structure of the children.....	14
4.2 Values priorities of children.....	16
4.3 Structure of teachers' value-related educational goals.....	19
4.4 Priorities of teachers' value-related educational goals.....	20
4.5 Children's behaviour rated by the teacher	21
5. Values and behaviours.....	23
6. Canons of values at Swiss German schools - An analysis of school mission statements.....	24
7. Follow up and thank you	25
8. Research Output	26
References.....	26

List of Tables and Figures

Table 1 Sample size and sex of pupils	7
Table 2 Age of pupils.....	7
Table 3 Country of birth	7
Table 4 Languages spoken at home	8
Table 5 Sample size and sex of teachers.....	8
Table 6 Age of teachers	9
Table 7 Country of birth	9
Table 8 Years of experience	9
Table 9 List and abbreviations of higher order values and their corresponding value types	11
Table 10 List and abbreviation/variable name of value-related educational goals	12

Table 11 Value priorities subsumed to value type; by gender (combined/boys/girls) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)	16
Table 12 Value priorities subsumed to higher order value; by gender (boys/girls) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)	18
Table 13 Value-related educational goals - subsumed to value type; combined (female/male) and point of data collection (T1 and T4).....	20
Table 14 Value-related educational goals subsumed to higher order value; combined (female/male) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)	21
Table 15 Variables and item of children's behaviour	22
Figure 1 Schwartz's structure of values (1992), own adaptation.....	10
Figure 2 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (T1).....	15
Figure 3 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (T4).....	15
Figure 4 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS (T1).....	19
Figure 5 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS (T4).....	20
Figure 6 Schwartz's structure of values (1992) with prototypical behaviours (Berson & Oreg, 2016)	22
Figure 7 Relationship of values and behaviours	23
Figure 8 Occurrence of individual value types	25

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
M	Mean
MDS	Multidimensional scaling
N	Sample size
PBVS-C	Picture-Based Value Survey for Children
PVQ	Portrait Value Questionnaire
SD	Standard deviation
t1	First data collection (spring 2021)
t2	Second data collection (autumn 2021)
t3	Third data collection (winter 2022)
t4	Forth data collection (summer 2022)

1. Introduction to this project report

This project report, which is an addition to the technical report, serves as the documentation of selected results of the data collection, in especially, how the realised samples of the pupils as well as the teachers are structured and in further insights in how the samples and specific variables changed over time in our longitudinal research project.

There were four survey periods throughout the project (t1 = spring 2021, t2 = autumn 2021, t3 = winter 2022, t4 = summer 2022). However, as we want to give a first insight in this report and not go into too much detail, we have sometimes listed the results of all data collections (t1-t4), but mostly only the results from the first (t1) and the last (t4) point of data collection. The reason for this is that we aim to illustrate if and what has changed over time (e.g., sample size, certain variables).

In a second part, a selection of initial analyses of the data will be presented. This section is intended to provide a first insight into selected research topics of the overall study. It should be emphasised once again that these are only individual results. If you are interested in more detailed results, please feel free to contact us (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-formation-in-school/>).

2. Results of data collections

2.1 Descriptive description of the sample

The anticipated sample of 1000 pupils and their class teachers in Switzerland was successfully recruited. Despite the corona pandemic, the interest and willingness to participate in our research project and thus the recruitment of the sample was very successful. The classes were recruited in the seven cantons of Aargau, Bern, Basel-Landschaft, Basel-Stadt, Lucerne, Solothurn and St. Gallen. The selection of schools ensured that a diverse sample is covered, with regard to ethnicity and cultural background, socioeconomic status, and children's life context (e.g., rural vs. urban environment). All of these cantons had already introduced the Lehrplan 21 (Curriculum 21) in their schools at the time of the survey. This was important to us, because the teachers were able to build on years of experience of implementing them. We checked that, taking into account drop-out, recruitment will be feasible.

The following section is divided in two parts. In the first section, the focus will be on the sample of the pupils (see 2.1.1). This includes a presentation of the sample size and sex of the pupils from the first point of data collection to the last point of data collection (table 1), information about the mean age of the pupils (table 2), the country of birth (table 3) and the languages that are spoken at home (table 4).

The second section will present the sample of the teachers (see 2.1.2), including the sample size and sex of the teachers (table 5), the age of the teachers (table 6), the country of birth (table 7) and the years of experience (table 8).

2.1.1 Sample of pupils

Table 1 *Sample size and sex of pupils*

	T1		T2		T3		T4	
Sex	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Boy	574	50.5	580	49.0	567	51.4	567	48.5
Girl	563	49.5	604	51.0	535	48.5	534	51.4
Missings	0	0	0	0	1	0.1	1	.1
Total	1137	100	1184	100	1103	100	1102	100

Table 2 *Age of pupils*

Age	T1	T2	T3	T4
Mean Age	6.82	7.35	7.75	8.04

Table 3 *Country of birth*

	T1		T2		T3		T4	
Country of birth	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
CH	862	76.1	948	80.1	899	81.5	924	83.8
other country	143	12.6	151	12.8	128	11.6	135	12.3
don't know	128	11.3	84	7.1	75	6.8	41	3.7
missings	4		1	0.1	1	0.1	2	0.2
Total	1137	100.00	1184	100.0	1103	100	1100	100

Country of birth specified

The children specified their countries of birth at the fourth survey point. The following countries were named (in order of frequency): Germany (n = 19), Italy (n = 10), Kosovo (n = 9), Eritrea and Turkey

(each country: n = 6), France, USA and Serbia (each country: n = 5), Brazil and Portugal (each country: n = 4), Macedonia, Slovenia, Spain, Syria, Thailand and Iraq (each country: n = 3), Albania, Bosnia, Sweden, Hungary, Croatia, Poland and Russia (each country: n = 2), Afghanistan, Argentina, Australia, Belarus, Belgium, Chile, Czech Republic, Egypt, England, Georgia, India, Lebanon, Morocco, Mexico, Montenegro, Netherlands, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Norway, Singapore, South Africa, Ukraine and Yemen (each country: n = 1).

Table 4 *Languages spoken at home*

Languages spoken at home	T1		T4	
	N	%	N	%
German (Swiss German or Standard German)	627	55.9	563	51.1
German (Swiss German or Standard German) and another language	339	30.2	436	39.5
Other Language (no German)	155	13.9	101	9.2
missings	16		2	.2
Total	1137	100.00	1102	100

2.1.2 Sample of teachers

Table 5 *Sample size and sex of teachers*

Sex	T1		T2		T3		T4	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Female	102	94.4	96	94.1	90	93.8	78	94.0
Male	6	5.6	6	5.9	6	6.2	5	6.0
Total	108	100.00	102	100.0	96	100	83	100

Table 6 *Age of teachers*

Age	T1	T2	T3	T4
Teachers	38.33	39.19	39.3	39.8

Table 7 *Country of birth*

Country of birth	T1		T4	
	N	%	N	%
CH	98	90.7	74	89.2
Argentina (Argentinien)	1	0.9	1	1.2
Germany (Deutschland)	6	5.7	5	6
France (Frankreich)	1	0.9	1	1.2
South Africa (Südafrika)	1	0.9	1	1.2
Czech Republic (Tschechien)	1	0.9	1	1.2
Total	108	100.00	74	89.2

Table 8 *Years of experience*

	T1		T2		T3		T4	
	N	M	N	M	N	M	N	M
Years of experience	108	12.83	102	13.45	96	13.2	83	13.78

3. Theoretical and methodical anchoring

How are values defined and how can they be organized?

Values express what is important to an individual important in life and what they strive for. They are at the centre of a person's self-concept and identity of a person (Hitlin & Piliavin 2004). Values are not only as fundamental abstract beliefs, but they are also inextricably linked to motivation and orientations and thus guide our actions (Bardi & Schwartz, 2003). In both adults' as well as children's values are considered to be relatively stable and are therefore regarded as guidelines in the life course of an individual (Schwartz, 1992).

A comprehensively established model on personal value orientations (value priorities and value structures) comes from the theory of human values by Shalom Schwartz (1992). Basic values are in this model organised in a circular structure and include the following ten basic values: universalism, benevolence, tradition, conformity, security, power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation and self-direction (figure 1, table 9). Moreover, Schwartz (1992, 1994, 2012) summarised these ten basic values along their motivational goals into a circular structure. This results in four higher-order value types. These include self-transcendence (universalism, benevolence), conservation (tradition, conformity, security), self-enhancement (power and achievement) and openness to change (hedonism, stimulation, self-direction).

Values lying next to each other in a circle show similarities in terms of their motivational focus and can be well with each other. In the case of the basic values universalism and benevolence, for example focus on fellow human beings and their needs are central, whereas the core values of achievement and power focus on the individual and his or her own needs.

Figure 1 Schwartz's structure of values (1992), own adaptation

Table 9 List and abbreviations of higher order values and their corresponding value types

Higher order value	Abbreviation/ name of item	Value type	Abbreviation/ name of item	Example item
Self-transcendence	SeTr	Universalism	UN	to make new friends
		Benevolence	BE	to help others
		Tradition	TR	to think of God
Conservation	Cons	Conservation	CO	to observe the rules
		Security	SE	to be safe
Self-enhancement	SeEn	Power	PO	to be rich and powerful
		Achievement	AC	to be the best
		Hedonism	HE	to enjoy life
Openness to change	OtC	Stimulation	ST	to do exciting things
		Self-direction	SD	to discover new things

How can we measure children's values?

The value priorities and the value structures of the pupils are measured by the Picture-Based Value Survey for Children (PBVS-C, Döring et al. 2010). For this purpose, 20 pictures are presented, in each of which a gender-neutral main figure performs a value-relevant action. Through the children can easily identify with the main character. The children assess how important the values depicted in the picture are and classify the pictures in a given answer format (important pictures at the top, unimportant below). For the basic value of benevolence, the main character helps a child to get up after a bicycle accident. The core value power is illustrated by the main character, who sits on a throne and appears rich and powerful. Through a picture in which the main figure is lying on a hammock in the sun and enjoys life, the basic value of hedonism is represented. A picture with the main character on a bicycle and a policeman putting a helmet on the child shows the basic value security ("being safe") (see figure 1 or table 1 for examples).

How can we measure teacher's value-related educational goals?

Teachers completed an online questionnaire on their value-related educational goals, using the well-established Portrait Values Questionnaire (PVQ-21, Schwartz et al., 2001). The PVQ-21 consists of 21

items that include a short verbal portrait describing a person's life goals or aspirations. In our survey, we did not focus on the teachers' personal values but on their value-related educational goals. These are defined as the values that the teachers want to promote in their class. With the use of a 6-point Likert scale, the teachers rate how much they want their students to resemble the person described in each item. In the process, it is ascertained how similar their students should be to the 21 value-oriented person descriptions. Several items represent each of the 10 basic values as defined by Schwartz (see table 12).

Table 10 *List and abbreviation/variable name of value-related educational goals*

Value	Variable	Item
Universalism	PVQ_UN1	They think it is important that every person in the world be treated equally. They believe everyone should have equal opportunities in life.
	PVQ_UN2	It is important to them to listen to people who are different from them. Even when they disagree with them, they still want to understand them.
	PVQ_UN3	They strongly believe that people should care for nature. Looking after the environment is important to them.
Benevolence	PVQ_BE1	It's very important to them to help the people around them. They want to care for their well-being.
	PVQ_BE2	It is important to them to be loyal to their friends. They want to devote themselves to people close to them.
Tradition	PVQ_TR1	It is important to them to be humble and modest. They try not to draw attention to themselves.
	PVQ_TR2	Tradition is important to them. They try to follow the customs handed down by their religion or their family.
Conservation	PVQ_CO1	They believe that people should do what they're told. They think people should follow rules at all times, even when no one is watching.
	PVQ_CO2	It is important to them always to behave properly. They want to avoid doing anything people would say is wrong.
Security	PVQ_SE1	It is important to them to live in secure surroundings. They avoid anything that might endanger their safety.

Power	PVQ_SE2	It is important to them that the government ensures their safety against all threats. They want the state to be strong so it can defend its citizens.
	PVQ_PO1	It is important to them to be rich. They want to have a lot of money and expensive things.
	PVQ_PO2	It is important to them to get respect from others. They want people to do what they say.
Achievement	PVQ_AC1	It's very important to them to show their abilities. They want people to admire what they do.
	PVQ_AC2	Being very successful is important to them. They hope people will recognise their achievements.
Hedonism	PVQ_HE1	Having a good time is important to them. They like to "spoil" themselves.
	PVQ_HE2	They seek every chance to have fun. It is important to them to do things that give them pleasure
Stimulation	PVQ_ST1	They like surprises and are always looking for new things to do. They think it is important to do lots of different things in life.
	PVQ_ST2	They look for adventures and like to take risks. They want to have an exciting life.
Self-direction	PVQ_SD1	Thinking up new ideas and being creative is important to them. They like to do things in their own original way.
	PVQ_SD2	It is important to them to make their own decisions about what they do. They like to be free and not depend on others.

How can we measure the value structure?

The analysis as well as the representation of the children's value structure was carried out by means of a multidimensional scaling (MDS). According to Borg (2010), the MDS contains different procedures with which objects are represented as points in a coordinate system in a two- or three-dimensional space. Based on a pairwise correlation matrix, the MDS refracts the ordinal information in a two-dimensional space and plots the data points along the two dimensions on the corresponding coordinate (Borg & Staufenbiel, 2007). According to Borg and Staufenbiel (2007, p. 160), the graphical representation of

the correlations between items in the form of points allows "the structure of the intercorrelations to be explored by eye" and thus makes it easier to grasp correlations.

Similar to the measurement of the children's value structure, we analysed the structure of the value-related educational goals with use of the MDS.

4. Selection of initial analyses of the sample

4.1 Value structure of the children

The MDS of our sample shows that children at primary school age already have a value structure that corresponds to Schwartz's (1992) value model (figure 1). This means that both the basic values hedonism, self-direction and stimulation versus the three values of tradition, conformity and security, as well as the universalism and benevolence vis-à-vis the basic values power and achievement are at the correct region. The MDS of the value structure is displayed below of the first and fourth data collections (figures 2 and 3).

Looking at differences from t1 to t4, one can see that the values that belong together (with the same colour) mostly get closer together. This means their correlation gets stronger. The distance from one item to the other shows the correlation between two items and serves as a measure of similarity.

The correlation is stronger the closer the points are to each other in space. As a result, one can say that the older the children get, the better they fit to the structure of Schwartz's value theory.

In both structures one can see the items that belong to a same value are in neighbouring regions and can be divided into the four higher order values.

Taking a closer look at the MDS of the values, one can see two outliers (TR2, AC2; the light blue marked). These can be explained due to the very heterogeneous cognitive and linguistic development of the children at this young age. It seems that not all children at this age are able to fulfil the cognitive and developmental requirements of the PBVS-C.

Figure 2 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (T1)

Figure 3 Value structure MDS, PBVS-C (T4)

4.2 Values priorities of children

The results on the value priorities in Table 10 provide information which values are important to the children, and which are not so important at the first and fourth point of data collection. The children's value priorities show that for both the children as a whole as well as broken down into girls and boys, benevolence is the most important value over all points of data collection. Promoting the well-being of the people close to them is at the top. At the lowest end of the hierarchy of values for the children is the value power. Social status, prestige and authority seem to be the least important for the children (girls and boys). Although the most important as well as the least important basic value of the children are the same, gender differences can be seen (e.g., security or hedonism), the girls prioritise (1) benevolence, (2) security, (3) universalism, whereas for boys on the second place of the value hierarchy is the value of hedonism instead of security, but only at the first point of data collection. At the last point of data collection, the boys prioritise (1) benevolence, (2) universalism and (3) hedonism. Explanatory approaches for the different prioritisation of values could lay in evolutionary psychology, in different socialisation conditions or in the social role theory, in which the origin of gender differences lays in the gender-specific division of labour.

Table 11 *Value priorities subsumed to value type; by gender (combined/boys/girls) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)*

Variable	T1									T4								
	combined			girls			boys			combined			girls			boys		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
UN	834	3.31	0.72	412	3.40	0.71	422	3.22	0.72	1102	3.47	0.65	534	3.57	0.60	567	3.37	.068
BE	834	3.53	0.68	412	3.72	0.64	422	3.34	0.66	1102	3.69	0.65	534	3.90	0.56	567	3.50	0.67

TR	834	2.93	0.71	412	3.01	0.71	422	2.85	0.71	1102	3.09	0.77	534	3.13	0.78	567	3.05	0.76
CO	834	2.72	0.59	412	2.73	0.58	422	2.71	0.59	1102	2.62	0.54	534	2.67	0.51	567	2.57	0.57
SE	834	3.33	0.74	412	3.46	0.71	422	3.21	0.75	1102	3.42	0.73	534	3.53	0.67	567	3.31	0.77
PO	834	2.35	0.92	412	2.20	0.81	422	2.51	1.00	1102	1.92	0.71	534	1.76	0.55	567	2.07	0.80
AC	834	2.89	0.78	412	2.76	0.74	422	3.03	0.81	1102	2.51	0.67	534	2.40	0.59	567	2.61	0.73
HE	834	3.17	0.73	412	3.08	0.71	422	3.25	0.75	1102	3.21	0.73	534	3.08	0.66	567	3.33	0.78
ST	834	2.92	0.81	412	2.79	0.76	422	3.04	0.85	1102	3.12	0.77	534	2.99	0.68	567	3.25	0.83
SD	834	2.84	0.67	412	2.84	0.63	422	2.84	0.70	1102	2.95	0.59	534	2.97	0.52	567	2.93	0.64

Looking at the four higher-order value types, the results show that both the total sample and the girls and boys rank self-transcendence as the most important higher-order value type (table 11). This is not surprising, since humanistic and universalistic basic values are at the top of the value hierarchy for both genders. The well-being of their fellow human beings and the protection of nature seem to be the primary concerns for the pupils from first to second grade. Girls give this more weight than boys. The value type of higher order self-enhancement, on the other hand, occupies the last place in the value hierarchy for both genders. Although social status, prestige and supremacy seem to be of little importance to the children, the findings indicate that these aspects are more important to boys than to girls. This also applies to the achievement value, which embodies personal success. It follows that both genders focus more on social relationships and other people than on themselves. Finally, the rankings of self-transcendence and self-enhancement confirm the motivational contrast the two occupy in Schwartz's theory of values (1992,

1994). The girls and boys follow different rankings when it comes to the second and third important value. In the case of girls, the hierarchy of values is in line with the overall sample at t1, whereas in the case of boys, preservation of the existing and openness to change are ranked the other way round. This means that girls place more value on tradition, conformity and security than boys. According to Schwartz (2006, 2009), self-protection as well as avoiding and coping with fear are more important to female first graders than to boys. For the latter, on the other hand, a challenging and exciting life and the enjoyment of life are more important. Accordingly, boys tend to be less characterised by anxiety and strive for personal development (Schwartz, 2006, 2009). This seems to change at the end of the second grade, when the order of the second and third important value changes for both girls and boys, and the boys' hierarchy of values is now in line with the overall sample.

Table 12 Value priorities subsumed to higher order value; by gender (boys/girls) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)

Variable	T1									T4								
	combined			girls			boys			combined			girls			boys		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
SeTr	834	3.42	0.52	412	3.56	0.49	422	3.28	0.52	1102	3.58	0.49	534	3.74	0.43	567	3.44	0.50
Cons	834	3.00	0.40	412	3.07	0.37	422	2.92	0.41	1102	3.04	0.41	534	3.11	0.38	567	2.98	0.42
SeEn	834	2.62	0.68	412	2.48	0.60	422	2.77	0.72	1102	2.21	0.57	534	2.08	0.46	567	2.34	0.63
OtC	834	2.97	0.40	412	2.90	0.38	422	3.04	0.41	1102	3.09	0.43	534	3.01	0.38	567	3.17	0.45

4.3 Structure of teachers' value-related educational goals

The MDS of our sample shows that primary school teachers' value-related educational goals have a structure that corresponds to Schwartz's (1992) value model (figure 1). The MDS of the structure of the value-related educational goals is displayed below of the first and fourth data collections (figures 4 and 5). Looking at differences from t1 to t4, one can see that the values that belong together (with the same colour) are close together. The overall structure shows that the variables that belong together differentiate outwards. At t1, the items were still quite close to the centre, but they have moved further outwards at t4. In both structures one can see the items that belong to a same value are in neighbouring regions and can be divided into the four higher order values.

Figure 4 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS (T1)

Figure 5 Value-related educational goals teachers MDS (T4)

4.4 Priorities of teachers' value-related educational goals

In the teachers' value-related educational goals the basic value of benevolence also takes first place at t1 as well as at t4. This means that the teachers want to transmit benevolent values at first place to their students. In contrast teachers are least likely to promote power-oriented values in the first and second grade.

Table 13 Value-related educational goals - subsumed to value type; combined (female/male) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)

Variable	T1			T4		
	combined			combined		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
UN	108	5.39	0.71	83	5.40	0.70
BE	108	5.59	0.58	83	5.52	0.54

TR	108	3.70	1.15	83	4.05	0.84
CO	108	3.44	1.34	83	3.67	1.04
SE	108	3.90	1.20	83	4.17	1.05
PO	108	3.00	1.15	83	3.10	1.10
AC	108	3.47	1.28	83	3.61	1.02
HE	108	4.87	.94	83	4.67	0.87
ST	108	3.98	1.00	83	4.08	0.89
SD	108	5.25	0.67	83	5.16	0.64

Table 14 Value-related educational goals subsumed to higher order value; combined (female/male) and point of data collection (T1 and T4)

Variable	T1			T4		
	combined			combined		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
SeTr	108	5.47	0.60	83	5.46	0.50
Cons	108	3.68	0.97	83	3.96	0.80
SeEn	108	3.23	1.02	83	3.36	0.97
OtC	108	4.70	0.64	83	4.64	0.61

4.5 Children's behaviour rated by the teacher

To find out whether there is a link between behaviours and values, children's behaviour was rated by the teachers. For this, the teachers were asked to assess children's behaviour as follows: For each child in her/his class, the teacher completed the 11-item Schoolchildren's Behaviour Scale as developed by Berson and Oreg (2016). The scale measures children's disciplined behaviour, learning-oriented behaviour, supportive behaviour, and achievement-oriented behaviour (see table 15). These four prototypical behaviours correspond to the higher-order value types (see figure 6).

Figure 6 Schwartz's structure of values (1992) with prototypical behaviours (Berson & Oreg, 2016)

Table 15 Variables and item of children's behaviour

Variable	Item
disciplined_1	is very disciplined in class.
disciplined_2	obeys the rules in class.
learning_oriented_1	finds it important to understand the subject matter covered in class.
learning_oriented_2	enjoys learning new things.
learning_oriented_3	asks many good questions in class.
supportive_1	helps other children in class.
supportive_2	is sensitive to the other children's needs.

supportive_3	rarely argues with other children.
achievement_1	is very competitive in class.
achievement_2	it is important for her/him to excel in class.
achievement_3	pays much attention to the feedback she/he gets.

5. Values and behaviours

The multilevel analysis points to positive correlations between the higher-order value types self-transcendence, conservation, and openness to change and value-related behaviours. Thus, with increasing importance of self-transcendence, the children's behaviour in class becomes more supportive, with increasing importance of conservation, the children's behaviour becomes more disciplined and with increasing importance of openness to change values, the children's behaviour becomes more learning-oriented. Self-enhancement is an exception: this higher-order value type does not have a significant effect on more achievement-oriented behaviour (figure 7).

Figure 7 Relationship of values and behaviours

6. Canons of values at Swiss German schools - An analysis of school mission statements

For some time now, value research has been concerned with individual and cultural value orientations. In this context, little attention has been paid to the area of schools. Values fulfil an important function in the school context. In addition to legally prescribed values, different school actors, such as teachers, are relevant factors in the value development of learners. Values in schools are expressed in mission statements, concrete corporate identity mission statements (CI mission statements), with which a school describes itself internally and externally. It is important for school staff to be aware of the value orientation. It is important for school officials to know the value orientation of schools in order to follow an orderly school routine, which ultimately increases the quality of a school. The question arises whether a canon of values in the CI mission statements of primary schools in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. To this end, the following primary research question: *Is it possible to identify a canon of values in the CI mission statements of primary schools?* In order to be able to answer this question, a qualitative study was conducted with a view to the corporate identity mission statement (CI mission statement) of primary schools in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. The CI mission statements were analysed with regard to the value types according to Schwartz (1992; 1994). The qualitative content analysis according to Mayring (2008) was used to analyse six Swiss-German CI mission statements. The qualitative study reveals a canon of values in the CI mission statements, whereby the value types universalism, benevolence and self-enhancement are clearly prevalent in comparison with all value types. It is also shown that the conditions of the school environment (migratory share of the municipality, number of teachers, etc.) have a significant influence on the school's success (proportion of migrants in the

community, number of teachers and students or school integration, respective segregation) have no influence on value preference.

Figure 8 Occurrence of individual value types

7. Follow up and thank you

A special thanks to all the participants, i.e., pupils and teachers in our VALISE research project at the Institute for Educational Sciences at the University of Basel. Furthermore, we want to thank all our research assistants who helped us collect the data of this immense sample. Thank you very much for your time and effort that made this research study possible.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact us via email valise@unibas.ch or check out the newest publications on our website (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-for-mation-in-school/>).

8. Research Output

The list of our research output will be regularly updated on our website (<https://bildungswissenschaften.unibas.ch/en/research/value-formation-in-school/>).

So far, two scientific articles were published (August 2022):

Oeschger, T., Makarova E., & Döring, A. (2022). Values in the School Curriculum from Teachers' Perspective: A mixed-methods Study. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, Volume 3. doi:10.1016/j.ijedro.2022.100190

Scholz-Kuhn, R., Oeschger, T., Makarova, E., & Döring A. (2021). Wertetransmission in der Schule: Eine Studie zu Wertehaltungen von Kindern und Lehrpersonen auf der Primarstufe. *Die Grundschulzeitschrift*.

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